

Studies on Polarographic Maxima of Nitrobenzaldehydes and Their Suppression by Some Ionic and Non-Ionic Surfactants

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Role of some ionic and non-ionic surfactants in the suppression of polarographic negative maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes (*ortho*-isomer does not yield maximum), in 4% (v/v) ethanolic solution has been studied at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in BR buffer of pH 7.0. It is observed that all types of surfactants (cationic, anionic and non-ionic) suppress the maxima, the cationic ones being the most effective. Their characteristic properties, viz. maximum suppression point (M.S.P.), specific suppression coefficient (S.S.C.) and critical micelle concentration (C.M.C.) have been determined. Relative efficacies of cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants in the suppression of the negative maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes have been determined on the basis of M.S.P. values.

HOLLECK and Exner¹ studied the effect of tylose, a surfactant, on the polarographic reduction waves of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes at different pH and observed that it not only suppressed the maxima but also altered the mechanism of the electrode process. However, studies on the polarographic maxima of nitrobenzaldehydes and their suppression by ionic surfactants and also by widely used non-ionic surfactants, such as Triton X-100 and gelatin have not been undertaken so far, and the title investigation has therefore been undertaken.

Experimental

The depolarizers, *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes (AnalaR) were recrystallized from ethanol before use. The other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The concentration of each of the depolarizers in the solution was kept at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ (in 4% ethanol). BR buffer of pH 7.0 acted as a supporting electrolyte.

A Toshniwal CLO2 manual polarograph in conjunction with a Toshniwal PL 50 polyflex galvanometer was used. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen was used for deaeration. The potentials were measured against S.C.E. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M KCl, open circuit), $h_{corr} = 62.4$ cm; $m = 3.0$ mg sec^{-1} ; $t = 3.02$ sec; $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.504$ $\text{mg}^{2/3} \text{sec}^{-1/6}$. The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction process was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon², which gave the value of n equal to 6 for *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde and 8 for *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde at pH 7.0.

The surfactants used were laurylpyridinium chloride (LPC), cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC), cetyl-

pyridinium bromide (CPB), cetyldimethylbenzylammonium chloride (CDBAC) and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) (all cationic); dodecylbenzene sulphonate (DBS), sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), Tergitol-7, Manoxol-OT and Manoxol-1B (all anionic); and Triton X-100, gelatin, Decon-90, ethyldigol and 2-ethoxyethanol (all non-ionic).

Results and Discussion

Representative Fig. 1 depicts the morphology of C-V curves of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde in the presence of increasing concentrations of LPC.

m/*p*-Nitrobenzaldehydes under the chosen experimental conditions yield sharp maxima which lie at -0.65 and -0.53 V (vs S.C.E.), respectively from the potential of the electrocapillary zero, which is -0.34 V (S.C.E.) under the same experimental conditions. However, *ortho*-isomer does not yield a maximum under these experimental conditions. The maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes lie on the negative side of the electrocapillary zero and hence these are of negative polarity³. The relative heights of the maxima are in the following order, *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde > *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde.

Effect of increasing concentrations of surfactants on the maxima: The effect of increasing concentrations of cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants on E_{max} and i_{max} has been studied and the values are listed in Table 1. A perusal of this Table reveals that E_{max} of both of the maxima gets shifted to less negative potentials (positive shift) as the concentration of cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants is increased. The decrease in the value of i_{max} from the stage when no surfactant is present to the point preceding the elimination of the maxima

Fig. 1. C-V Curves of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde in the presence of increasing concentrations of LPC. Each curve starts at -0.2 V.

(Table 1 contd.)

<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde			<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde			SLS		Tergitol-7		Manoxol-OT		Manoxol-IB		Triton X-100**		Gelatin**		Decon-90**											
[Surfactant] <i>M</i>	- <i>E</i> _{max} V (S.C.E.)	<i>i</i> _{max} µA	[Surfactant] <i>M</i>	- <i>E</i> _{max} V (S.C.E.)	<i>i</i> _{max} µA	× 10 ⁵	× 10 ⁵	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴	× 10 ⁴										
0	0.65	49.40	0	0.53	29.40	2.0	0.64	39.90	0.5	0.52	27.65	0.2	0.64	43.32	1.0	0.53	26.60	0.4	0.64	43.32	2.0	0.52	26.95	0.8	0.64	42.94	0.8	0.53	26.60
0.5 × 10 ⁵	0.64	42.66	1.0 × 10 ⁵	0.52	25.20	4.0	0.63	31.16	0.9	0.52	23.80	0.5	0.63	36.48	3.0	0.52	23.10	0.6	0.63	33.06	5.0	0.51	22.05	4.0	0.62	32.68	2.0	0.52	23.45
1.0 × 10 ⁵	0.63	33.44	3.0 × 10 ⁵	0.51	22.40	6.0	0.62	25.84	1.8	0.51	19.25	1.0	0.62	27.36	6.0	0.50	18.90	8.0	0.62	28.12	8.0	0.50	19.25	6.0	0.61	26.50	5.6	0.52	18.90
1.5 × 10 ⁵	0.62	26.60	6.0 × 10 ⁵	0.50	19.25	8.0 I step	0.540*	20.54*	3.0 I step	0.470*	17.50*	1.0 I step	0.547*	20.14*	8.0 I step	0.480*	17.15*	1.0 I step	0.530*	20.90*	7.0 I step	0.485*	17.15*	7.0 I step	0.530*	20.90*	9.88*	0.52	17.50*
2.0 × 10 ⁵	0.538*	21.28*	8.0 II step	1.282*	10.50*	8.0 II step	1.352*	9.88*	3.0 II step	1.305*	9.80*	1.0 II step	1.345*	9.12*	8.0 II step	1.315*	9.80*	1.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.285*	10.50*	7.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	9.88*	0.51	21.95
2.0 III step	1.330*	9.88*	8.0 III step	1.615*	7.00*	8.0 III step	1.615*	7.00*	3.0 III step	1.620*	6.65*	1.0 III step	1.610*	5.60*	8.0 III step	1.610*	5.60*	1.0 III step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 III step	1.513*	7.00*	7.0 III step	1.513*	7.00*	9.88*	0.52	22.05
0.5 × 10 ⁵	0.65	40.66	1.0 × 10 ⁵	0.53	25.90	0.4 × 10 ⁴	0.64	43.32	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.52	26.95	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.64	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.64	42.94	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.53	26.60
1.0 × 10 ⁵	0.64	32.68	3.0 × 10 ⁵	0.52	23.10	0.6 × 10 ⁴	0.63	33.06	5.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	22.05	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.63	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	32.68	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.52	23.45
1.5 × 10 ⁵	0.64	28.50	6.0 × 10 ⁵	0.50	18.90	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.62	28.12	8.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.25	1.0 × 10 ⁴	0.62	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	1.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	1.0 × 10 ⁴	0.61	26.50	5.6 × 10 ⁴	0.52	18.90
2.0 × 10 ⁵	0.535*	21.28*	7.0 I step	0.463*	17.05*	1.0 I step	0.500*	19.76*	9.0 I step	0.465*	17.85*	1.0 I step	0.500*	19.76*	9.0 I step	0.465*	17.85*	1.0 I step	0.530*	20.90*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	1.0 I step	0.530*	20.90*	9.88*	0.52	17.50*
2.0 II step	1.350*	9.88*	7.0 II step	1.286*	10.50*	1.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	9.0 II step	1.285*	10.50*	1.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	9.0 II step	1.285*	10.50*	1.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	1.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	9.88*	0.51	21.95
0.5 × 10 ⁵	0.64	43.70	2.0 × 10 ⁵	0.53	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25
0.5 × 10 ⁵	0.62	34.20	4.0 × 10 ⁵	0.52	22.05	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95
1.0 × 10 ⁵	0.60	25.08	6.0 × 10 ⁵	0.51	18.90	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60
2.0 × 10 ⁵	0.530*	19.76*	7.0 I step	0.462*	17.85*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.14*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.14*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.90*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.90*	9.88*	0.52	17.50*
2.0 II step	1.338*	9.88*	7.0 II step	1.282*	10.50*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	9.88*	0.51	21.95
0.2 × 10 ⁵	0.64	43.70	2.0 × 10 ⁵	0.53	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25
0.5 × 10 ⁵	0.62	34.20	4.0 × 10 ⁵	0.52	22.05	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95
1.0 × 10 ⁵	0.60	25.08	6.0 × 10 ⁵	0.51	18.90	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60
2.0 × 10 ⁵	0.530*	19.76*	7.0 I step	0.462*	17.85*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.14*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.14*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.90*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.90*	9.88*	0.52	17.50*
2.0 II step	1.338*	9.88*	7.0 II step	1.282*	10.50*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	9.88*	0.51	21.95
0.2 × 10 ⁵	0.64	43.70	2.0 × 10 ⁵	0.53	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25
0.5 × 10 ⁵	0.62	34.20	4.0 × 10 ⁵	0.52	22.05	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95
1.0 × 10 ⁵	0.60	25.08	6.0 × 10 ⁵	0.51	18.90	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60
2.0 × 10 ⁵	0.530*	19.76*	7.0 I step	0.462*	17.85*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.14*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.14*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.90*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.90*	9.88*	0.52	17.50*
2.0 II step	1.338*	9.88*	7.0 II step	1.282*	10.50*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	9.88*	0.51	21.95
0.2 × 10 ⁵	0.64	43.70	2.0 × 10 ⁵	0.53	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25	0.8 × 10 ⁴	0.65	42.56	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	26.25
0.5 × 10 ⁵	0.62	34.20	4.0 × 10 ⁵	0.52	22.05	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95	0.5 × 10 ⁴	0.64	38.00	4.0 × 10 ⁴	0.51	21.95
1.0 × 10 ⁵	0.60	25.08	6.0 × 10 ⁵	0.51	18.90	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60	2.0 × 10 ⁴	0.60	28.12	6.0 × 10 ⁴	0.50	19.60
2.0 × 10 ⁵	0.530*	19.76*	7.0 I step	0.462*	17.85*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.14*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.14*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.90*	7.0 I step	0.468*	17.50*	4.0 I step	0.530*	20.90*	9.88*	0.52	17.50*
2.0 II step	1.338*	9.88*	7.0 II step	1.282*	10.50*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	7.0 II step	1.300*	9.80*	4.0 II step	1.320*	10.64*	9.88*	0.51	21.95
0.2 × 10 ⁵	0.64	43.70	2.0 × 10 ⁵	0.53																									

(Table 1 contd.)

$\times 10^3$		Ethylidigol		$\times 1,^*$	
0.2	0.64	40.28	0.7	0.52	26.25
0.4	0.62	32.68	1.0	0.50	22.75
0.6	0.60	26.60	2.0	0.5J	19.25
1.0	I step	0.540*	20.52*	I step	0.475*
	II step	1.320*	10.64*	II step	1.312*
				III step	1.632*
					6.65*
$\times 10^3$		2-Ethoxyethanol		$\times 10^4$	
0.6	0.60	44.08	1.0	0.50	26.60
1.5	0.56	37.24	3.0	0.49	23.10
2.5	0.54	25.84	4.2	0.49	18.20
8.0	I step	0.530*	16.72*	I step	0.460*
	II step	1.320*	10.26*	II step	1.288*
				III step	1.560*
					5.60*

* value of $E_{1,1}$; + value of i_d , and
 ** concentrations expressed in percentage.

is different for both the isomers. The decrease in i_{max} is in the following order, *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde > *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde.

After the suppression of the maxima by requisite amounts of the surfactants, each depolarizer yields a well-defined wave [Fig. 1 (6)] which is diffusion-controlled and irreversible.

Characteristic properties of the surfactants vis-avis their relative efficacies in suppression of the maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes : The values of characteristic properties, viz. M.S.P., S.S.C. and C.M.C. of the surfactants in respect to the maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes were determined⁴⁻⁶ and have been listed in Table 2. A perusal of this Table reveals that M.S.P. and S.S.C. values for cationic surfactants are much less than those for anionic ones. It follows from this that the amount of ionic surfactants required to suppress maxima of similar sign is greater than those possessing dissimilar charges⁷.

Antweiler⁸ has unambiguously proved that the polarographic maxima of the first kind are due to tangential streaming of the solution with respect to

the drop. The success of a maxima suppressor depends on its capability of curbing this streaming. Since the maxima in the present study lie on the negative side of the electro-capillary zero, the cationic surfactants will move right up to the mercury surface and the anionic ones are likely to move at a distance somewhere in the double layer. A cationic surfactant will prevent streaming more effectively as compared to an anionic one with identical hydrocarbon chain. This is supported by the fact that LPC is more effective than SLS, though both the surfactants have the same carbon chain length.

On the basis of M.S.P. values, the order of relative efficacies of cationic, anionic and non-ionic surfactants in suppressing the negative maxima of *m*- and *p*-nitrobenzaldehydes has been established as follows :

Cationic surfactants : LPC and CPC possess the same polar head but different carbon chain length. The following order exists for their efficacies : CPC > LPC. Thus, with the same polar head the efficacy of a cationic surfactant increases with the increase in carbon chain length.

In the case of CTAB and CDBAC which possess the same carbon chain length but different polar head, it is found that the former is more effective than the latter. The efficacies of cationic surfactants are in the following order, CTAB > CDBAC > CPC > LPC > CPB.

Anionic surfactants : In the case of Manoxol-IB and Manoxol-OT which possess the same polar head but different carbon chain lengths, it is found that the latter with longer carbon chain is more effective in suppressing these negative maxima. The efficacies of the anionic surfactants are in the following order, SLS > DBS > Tergitol-7 > Manoxol-OT > Manoxol-IB.

Non-ionic surfactants : Non-ionic or amphoteric substances suppress maxima on the basis of preferential adsorption on the mercury drop. The

TABLE 2—M.S.P., S.S.C. AND C.M.C. VALUES FOR IONIC AND NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS IN RESPECT OF THE MAXIMA OF *m*- AND *p*-NITROBENZALDEHYDES

Surfactants	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde			<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde		
	M.S.P.	S.S.C.	C.M.C.	M.S.P.	S.S.C.	C.M.C.
	<i>M</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>M</i>
LPC	1.8×10^{-6}	5.3×10^{-8}	8.0×10^{-6}	7.0×10^{-9}	2.4×10^{-9}	3.0×10^{-9}
CPC	1.7×10^{-6}	5.1×10^{-8}	7.0×10^{-6}	6.8×10^{-9}	2.0×10^{-9}	4.0×10^{-9}
CPB	2.0×10^{-6}	5.4×10^{-8}	4.0×10^{-6}	7.0×10^{-9}	3.1×10^{-9}	5.0×10^{-9}
GDBAC	9.2×10^{-6}	4.0×10^{-8}	5.0×10^{-6}	4.8×10^{-9}	1.6×10^{-9}	2.0×10^{-9}
CTAB	9.0×10^{-6}	3.5×10^{-8}	6.0×10^{-6}	2.0×10^{-9}	7.0×10^{-9}	8.0×10^{-9}
DBS	7.9×10^{-6}	2.3×10^{-8}	4.3×10^{-6}	7.5×10^{-9}	2.5×10^{-9}	4.3×10^{-9}
SLS	7.1×10^{-6}	1.2×10^{-8}	3.5×10^{-6}	2.8×10^{-9}	8.0×10^{-9}	9.0×10^{-9}
Tergitol-7	9.7×10^{-6}	5.3×10^{-8}	4.0×10^{-6}	7.8×10^{-9}	2.8×10^{-9}	2.3×10^{-9}
Manoxol-OT	1.0×10^{-4}	5.7×10^{-6}	5.2×10^{-3}	8.9×10^{-3}	3.5×10^{-5}	5.4×10^{-5}
Manoxol-IB	3.9×10^{-3}	9.2×10^{-3}	1.5×10^{-3}	6.4×10^{-3}	2.5×10^{-3}	4.0×10^{-3}
Triton X-100*	6.9×10^{-4}	3.5×10^{-4}	—	6.6×10^{-4}	9.5×10^{-5}	—
Gelatin*	2.9×10^{-8}	7.4×10^{-4}	—	9.9×10^{-4}	5.3×10^{-4}	—
Decon-90*	5.5×10^{-3}	1.9×10^{-3}	—	9.8×10^{-3}	3.2×10^{-3}	—
Ethylidigol	1.0×10^{-3}	3.8×10^{-3}	—	2.8×10^{-3}	8.9×10^{-3}	—
2-Ethoxyethanol	7.8×10^{-3}	2.0×10^{-3}	—	4.9×10^{-3}	1.8×10^{-3}	—

* M.S.P., S.S.C. and C.M.C. values in percentage.

efficacy of these suppressors depends upon the potential range of the maxima. Different non-ionic suppressors are adsorbed on the mercury drop to different extent at a given potential. The order of the efficacies is as follows, Triton X-100 > gelatin > Decon-90 > ethyldigol > 2-ethoxyethanol.

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